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Editorial

The Audacity of the Impossible

The Audacity of Hope: Thoughts on Reclaiming the American Dream is a bestseller by Barack Obama. Obama was cast into the national spotlight when asked to deliver a keynote speech at the 2004 Democratic Presidential Convention. This book consists of a litany of his fundamental beliefs that have contributed to his personal and political values. . It is the “audacity of hope” that leads us to believe that we can do better. It is the “audacity of hope” that allows us to take charge of our own fate. It is the “audacity of hope” that instils in us the desire for strong leadership. The fundamental beliefs Obama shares reflect those noted in women leadership literature. The beliefs include (a) staying true to core values, (b) selecting role models and mentors. (c) establishing a support system, (d) learning to compete in an unfamiliar environment, (e) overcoming stereotypes, and (f) maintaining political rightness.

In Pope “Francis there is real cause to hope after his dazzling start that we are at the onset of a Vatican Spring that could see the Catholic Church turning the corner towards a more democratic and open institution as advocated by Pope John XIII,” writes *Times of Malta* already in 2013.

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Rev Arturo Sosa, Superior General of the Jesuits, speaks further of the audacity of the impossible. “We are called to give an audacious response to the unexpected crises of the present moment without diminishing our engagement with human tragedies that go beyond the present moment, tragedies like the migration of persons forced to leave their homelands because of poverty, violence, or lack of a future for their families.”

This is the audacity of the impossible that allowed Mary of Nazareth to trust what was announced to her by the Archangel Gabriel. Such an audacity of the impossible sustained the former Jesuit General, Pedro Arrupe’s decision to give an immediate response to migrants and refugees.

The General continues: “We are asked to be audacious with what we have, with all that we have received from the Lord who loves us. We may produce five more talents or two, according to the measure of the gift received.”

“Every priest is a gift for humanity, a person acting for the good of the human family, which is the main focus of his life,” said Archbishop Thomas Meenamparampil of Guwahati, in remarks view of the conclusion of the Year for Priests in 2010. “In the life of a priest, thanks to the presence of God, the impossible becomes possible. A priest brings joy into people’s lives, and receives joy from his mission.” This year he challenges us with the book, *Attempt the Impossible!* which will be reviewed in the next issue of our journal.

Christmas is truly an attempt at the impossible, an audacity of joy. Even in our darkest timings, the coming of Christ brings joy.

We are Easter people, and for us, Christmas will always come with its audacity of joy. In spite of ...! As Christians, we can trust in and hope for the audacity of the impossible!

The Editor

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